

**Chromatographic Studies of Metal Complexes.
Part-III. Adsorption, Dissociation, and
Intermediate Complex Formation of some
Square-planar Biguanide Complexes
of Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Palladium(II)
on Silica Gel**

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A systematic tlc study of some square-planar bis(biguanide or substituted biguanide) metal(II) complexes is reported here.

Experimental

The complexes were synthesised by reported methods¹ and their purity was checked by elemental analysis and spectral measurements. Silica gel H (Merck) was used as the adsorbent and the plates were made following Stahl's method². Experimental techniques were followed as described elsewhere³⁻⁵.

The nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes were detected with an ethanolic solution of dithiooxamide (rubeanic acid), which produced blue and green spots, respectively. The palladium(II) complexes were detected with an acidified ethanolic solution of dithiooxamide, which produced yellow spots. Aqueous solutions of KCl, K₂SO₄, Na₂S₂O₃ and KNaC₄H₄O₆ were used as developer solvents. For the preparation of developers d and f, silica gel was stirred with an aqueous solution

of KCl for 1 h and the filtrate was mixed with the particular electrolyte (Table 1).

TABLE I—ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF THE COMPLEXES IN DIFFERENT DEVELOPER SOLVENTS

Compd.	Developer*	λ_{max} nm	Identified specie;
[Ni(RbigH) ₂]Cl ₂ (R=H, Me, Ph, etc.)	a, b	460	[Ni(R-bigH) ₂]Cl ₂
	d, e	400	[Ni(H ₂ O) ₆]Cl ₂
[Ni en(bigH ₂)]Cl ₂	a, b, d, e	460	[Ni en(bigH ₂)]Cl ₂
[Cu(RbigH) ₂]Cl ₂ (R=H, Me, Ph, etc.)	a, c	530	[Cu(RbigH) ₂]Cl ₂
	f, g	650	[Cu(RbigH)(H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂
	h	800	[Cu(H ₂ O) ₆]Cl ₂
[Cu en(bigH)]Cl ₂	a, c	520	[Cu en(bigH)]Cl ₂
	f, g	650	[Cu en(bigH)]Cl ₂
	i	800	[Cu(H ₂ O) ₆]Cl ₂
[Pd(bigH) ₂]Cl ₂	a, c	300	[Pd(bigH) ₂]Cl ₂
	f, g	345	[Pd(bigH)(H ₂ O)]Cl ₂
	j	480	[PdCl ₄] ²⁻
[Pd(bigH)(H ₂ O)]Cl ₂	a, c	345	[Pd(bigH)(H ₂ O)]Cl ₂
	g	345	[Pd(bigH)(H ₂ O)]Cl ₂
	a, i	480	[PdCl ₄] ²⁻

*Developers: a=water, b=0.2 M KCl, c=0.5 M KCl, d=silica gel digested with 0.2 M KCl solution and the solution collected after filtration, e=0.2 M KCl containing 0.01 M HCl, f=silica gel digested with 0.5 M KCl and then filtered, g=0.5 M KCl containing 0.01 M HCl, h=0.5 M KCl containing 0.05 M HCl, i=0.5 M KCl containing 0.1 M HCl, j=0.5 M KCl containing 0.2 M HCl.

Results and Discussion

When the cationic nickel(II), copper(II) and palladium(II) complexes were developed with water, they all remained at the base line observed in paper chromatography⁸⁻⁵. This is not surprising because silica gel ($\equiv\text{Si}-\text{OH}$) becomes negative in contact with water and easily captures the positively charged complex species. However, such binding can be weakened considerably by using a suitable electrolyte⁵. With different electrolytes such as KCl, K₂SO₄, Na₂S₂O₃, KNaC₄H₄O₆, etc. all the nickel(II) complexes show the same high R_F values exhibited by hexaaquanickel(II) ion. For the copper(II) complexes, R_F values differed from complex to complex as well as from that of the aquacopper(II) ion. Movement of the palladium(II) complexes on the silica gel bed was very slow, and consequently these complexes showed low R_F values.

The results show that all the nickel(II) complexes have same R_F value (0.93) in 0.2 M KCl, K₂SO₄, Na₂S₂O₃ and KNaC₄H₄O₆ developers, and the value is equal to the R_F value of the hexaaquanickel(II) ion. All these findings can be explained by considering ion-exchange phenomena between silica gel and the developer electrolyte³ which generates free acid. This acid easily decomposes the spot of bis(biguanide) nickel(II) chloride into the corresponding hexaaquanickel(II) ion.

Biguanide is highly basic (pK₁=12.5 at 32°) and protonation of this ligand bonded to the metal atom is possible. This catalyses dissociation of the chelate ring from the central metal atom⁶.

That the behaviour of the copper(II) complexes on silica gel is quite different from that of the nickel(II) complexes is revealed from the following R_F values in aqueous KCl (0.5 M) developer: [Cu(bigH)₂]Cl₂=0.66, [Cu(MebigH)₂]Cl₂=0.56, [Cu(EtbigH)₂]Cl₂=0.46, [Cu(PrbigH)₂]Cl₂=0.35, [Cu(PhbigH)₂]Cl₂=0.32, [Cu en(bigH)₂]Cl₂=0.45, and [Cu(H₂O)₆]Cl₂=0.78. This sequence of values means that bis(biguanide)copper(II) complexes persist either as actual bis(biguanide) or substituted biguanide copper(II) complexes or as diaquamono(biguanide)copper(II) complexes because of the liberation of acid from silica gel. It is known that at pH 4-5.4, bis(biguanide)copper(II) ion dissociates diaquamono(biguanide)copper(II) which at pH < 4 dissociates to hexaaquacopper(II) ion^{1,7}.

As the chain length of the alkyl substituent in the biguanide increases, the R_F values of the corresponding copper(II) complexes decrease because of the enhanced insolubility of the complexes in the aqueous KCl developer^{5,8}, and the following solubility order is observed: [Cu(bigH)₂]Cl₂ > [Cu(MebigH)₂]Cl₂ > [Cu(EtbigH)₂]Cl₂ > [Cu(PrbigH)₂]Cl₂. With K₂SO₄ as the developer solvent, all the bis(biguanide)copper(II) complexes remained at the point of application because of the extreme insolubility of the sulphate salt¹. In Na₂S₂O₃ developer, all the copper(II) complexes moved to the solvent front and showed high R_F values (1.00), possibly because of the reduction of copper(II) to copper(I) species followed by the formation of anionic copper(I) complexes. In KNaC₄H₄O₆ developer, all the copper(II) complexes also show R_F = 1.00, indicating that these complexes are not being chromatographed as genuine complexes but as some tartarato-copper(II) species.

The movement of the palladium(II) complexes on the silica gel bed is very slow because of their lower solubility in aqueous KCl developer. However, with a high concentration of KCl (0.5M) these complexes move but their spot sizes are too large (~3.5 cm). At a low acid concentration (0.01-0.1 M HCl) and higher chloride ion concentration (0.5 M KCl) bis(biguanide)-palladium(II) chloride dissociates into dichloromono(biguanide)palladium(II), [Pd(bigH)Cl₂], which may further dissociate into tetrachloropalladate(II) ion, [PdCl₄]²⁻, at a much higher acid concentration⁹ (0.15-0.4 M HCl) (Table 1). The large size of the spot indicates that [Pd(bigH)₂]Cl₂ might not be chromatographed as the actual complex since the acid liberated from silica gel and the large amount of chloride ion present in the developer solvent helps dissociation of bis(biguanide)palladium(II) chloride to dichloromono(biguanide)palladium(II). Formation of dichloromono(biguanide) palladium(II), was verified by

comparing the spectra of $[\text{Pd}(\text{bigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{-}[\text{PdCl}_4]$ in different developer solvents and by comparing the R_F values of $[\text{Pd}(\text{bigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ (0.44), $[\text{Pd}(\text{bigH})\text{Cl}_2]$ (0.51) and $\text{Li}_2\text{-}[\text{PdCl}_4]$ (1.00). The possibility of the formation of $[\text{PdCl}_4]^{2-}$ can easily be eliminated since $[\text{PdCl}_4]^{2-}$ being anionic exhibited a high R_F (1.00) value and exhibited a completely different spectrum from the spectra of $[\text{Pd}(\text{bigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ and $[\text{Pd}(\text{bigH})\text{Cl}_2]$.

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